

(1.7 g) is obtained. It is crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 143° (Found: N, 14.93; S, 22.53. $C_{14}H_{13}N_2S_2$ requires N, 14.63; S, 22.30%). This has been identified as 1,5-diphenyl-2,4-dithiobiuret (IIa) on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample⁸.

When the debenzylations of other 2-S-benzyl-1,5-diaryl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (Ib and Ic) were carried out with thiocarbamide in presence of pyridine in an ethanolic medium, the related products were obtained (IIb, m.p. 156°; Found: N, 13.56; S, 19.25. $C_{14}H_{13}N_2S_2Cl$ requires N, 13.06; S, 19.91% and IIc, m.p. 145°; Found: N, 13.26; S, 20.34. $C_{14}H_{13}N_2S_2Cl$ requires N, 13.06; S, 19.91%).

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Some Interesting Reactions of N-Phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl Chloride

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CHEMISTRY of N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I) with special reference to its application as an important intermediate in heterocyclic synthesis has been exhaustively investigated in this laboratory. The present note describes the intramolecular reaction of I in presence of anhydrous aluminium trichloride and intermolecular reaction in presence of aqueous ethanol and mixture of chloroform and aqueous ethanol in different proportions.

When N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride is boiled with anhydrous aluminium trichloride in dry diethyl ether medium for 4 hr. evolution of hydrogen chloride is observed. The reaction mixture on fractional distillation gives an oily product, b.p. 248°. It is identified as 2-chlorobenzothiazole (II) on the basis of its reaction with phenyl thiocarbamide in acetone medium when 1-(phenylformamidino)-1-phenyl thiocarbamide hydrochloride (III), m.p. 158° is isolated¹. The formation of 2-chlorobenzothiazole (II) may be explained as follows:

When rectified spirit is added to a chilled N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I) solution with stirring, a pale yellow solid, m.p. 118° is obtained. It is identified as 3-oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (IV) on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample².

When the same reaction of I is carried out with a mixture of chloroform and rectified spirit (1 : 1, v/v), only IV is obtained. However, the reaction of I with a mixture of chloroform and rectified spirit (2 : 1, v/v) gives IV and also 5-oxo-4-phenyl-2-phenylimino-1,3,4-dithiazolidine (V). The latter has been identified on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample³. As the ratio of chloroform in the mixture of chloroform and rectified spirit is increased, (3 : 1, v/v), V is formed almost exclusively. The IV and V may form as shown below.

No definite reaction mechanism could be established for the formation of IV and V. However, it is almost clear that the ratio of IV and V formed is dependant upon the concentration of rectified spirit. In presence of higher concentration of rectified spirit, more of IV is formed while in lower concentration of rectified spirit, V is the major product.

Experimental

The required N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I) has been prepared as usual⁴.

Intramolecular cyclisation of N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I) in presence of anhydrous aluminium trichloride; Formation of 2-chlorobenzothiazole (II):

Anhydrous aluminium trichloride (16 g) is gradually added to an ice cold solution of I in dry diethyl ether (0.1 M; 21 g in 75 ml), maintaining the temperature at -5° . After complete addition, the reaction mixture is allowed to stand for 30 min below 10° and then refluxed for 3 hr. It is then cooled and crushed ice (~ 100 g) is gradually added to decompose the probable aluminium trichloride complex. The resultant oily mass separated at the bottom is repeatedly extracted with diethyl ether. The ethereal solution on fractional distillation gives a fraction collected at $245-248^{\circ}$ in the form of a viscous oily liquid (Found: N, 8.48; S, 18.02. C_7H_4NSCl requires N, 8.26; S, 18.88%). It is identified as 2-chlorobenzothiazole (II) on the basis of its interaction with phenyl thiocarbamide in acetone medium, when 1-(phenylformamidino)-1-phenyl thiocarbamide hydrochloride (III), m.p. 158° is obtained (Found: N, 18.31; S, 9.88. $C_{14}H_{18}N_4S_2Cl$ requires N, 18.23; S, 10.42%). The latter also gives picrate, m.p. 142° . Both these products are identified on the basis of m.m.p. with authentic samples¹.

Intermolecular condensation of N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I): Formation of 3-oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (IV) and 5-oxo-4-phenyl-2-phenylimino-1,3,4-dithiazolidine (V):

(a) *Reaction in aqueous ethanol:* N-Phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (I) (0.1 M; 21 g) is cooled to 0° and chilled aqueous ethanol (25 ml) is added. An extremely vigorous and exothermic reaction is observed and almost immediately a pale yellow solid separates out. It is filtered, washed with a little ethanol and crystallized from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 118° (Found: N, 9.88; S, 21.92. $C_{14}H_{10}N_2S_2O$ requires N, 9.79; S, 22.39%). It is identified as 3-oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (IV) on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample².

(b) *Reaction in a mixture of aqueous ethanol-chloroform (1 : 1, v/v):* To N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (21 g) is gradually added a mixture of chloroform aqueous ethanol (1 : 1, v/v; 50 ml) at 0° . A vigorous exothermic reaction, accompanied by evolution of hydrogen chloride

is observed and almost immediately a pale yellow solid separates out. It is filtered, washed with a little aqueous ethanol and crystallized from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 118° (Found: N, 10.05; S, 22.55. $C_{14}H_{10}N_2S_2O$ requires N, 9.79; S, 22.39%). It is identified as 3-oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (IV) on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample².

(c) *Reaction in a mixture of aqueous ethanol-chloroform (1 : 2, v/v):* To an ice cold N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (21 g) is added a chilled mixture (75 ml) of chloroform-aqueous ethanol (2 : 1, v/v) when a vigorous reaction is noticed and a pale yellow solid separates out. It is filtered, washed with a little aqueous ethanol and crystallized from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 118° . It is identified as 3-oxo-4-phenyl-5-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidine (IV) as usual.

The filtrate, on addition of petroleum ether, affords a semisolid mass which on trituration several times with petroleum ether followed by ethanol is converted into a pale yellow solid, crystallized from glacial acetic acid/benzene/chlorobenzene, m.p. 245° (Found: N, 9.82; S, 22.45. $C_{14}H_{10}N_2S_2O$ requires N, 9.79; S, 22.39%). It is identified as 5-oxo-4-phenyl-2-phenylimino-1,3,4-dithiazolidine (V) on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample³.

(d) *Reaction in a mixture of aqueous ethanol-chloroform (1 : 3, v/v):* To N-phenyl-S-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (21 g) is added a mixture (100 ml) of aqueous ethanol-chloroform (1 : 3, v/v) at 0° and the reaction mixture is allowed to stand below 10° for about 30 min. A very mild reaction is noticed. The reaction mixture is then allowed to stand for 3 hr at room temperature and treated with excess petroleum ether when a semisolid mass is obtained. This, on trituration several times with petroleum ether followed by ethanol, affords a pale yellow solid crystallized from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 245° . This is identified as 5-oxo-4-phenyl-2-phenylimino-1,3,4-dithiazolidine (V) on the basis of m.m.p. with an authentic sample³.

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Studies on 2-pyrazolin-5-one Derivatives

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In our earlier communications, we reported that 5-pyrazolone¹⁻⁴ and its derivatives, 4-acetyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one⁵ and 2-pyrazolin-5-thione⁶, were